

COALESCE

Co-creating the EU Competence Centre for
Science Communication

Deliverable 6.2

Communication and Dissemination Guide for National and Regional Hubs and Networks

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1 Introduction

1.1 About COALESCE

The Coordinated Opportunities for Advanced Leadership and Engagement in Science Communication in Europe (COALESCE) project is funded by the European Commission (EC) to establish a European Competence Centre for Science Communication and an associated Science Communication Academy (Competence Centre and Academy). The Competence Centre will be a virtual platform, offering services, tools and resources through a network of physical National and Regional (N&R) hubs. The Competence Centre will be developed through consolidation of insights from past and ongoing research projects, including those funded under the EU 'Science with and for Society' (SwafS-19) programme as part of Horizon 2020, namely TRESKA, NEWSERA, PARCOS, GlobalScape, QUEST, ENJOI, CONCISE and RETHINK. The role of the Competence Centre is to further develop and mainstream science communication knowledge and to foster connections between science and society. In this context, the term science also refers to the related fields of technology, engineering, arts and mathematics (together known as STEAM).

The Competence Centre will be reinforced by the External Stakeholder Panel (ESP), which will be made up of topic networks (including those connected with climate; water, ocean and soils; AI and digital transformation; and health and vaccines); national, international and regional networks of science communication, science journalism or related areas; professional research networks and institutions; university alliances; EU-funded projects and EU platforms; policy-focused institutions, as well as a network of distributed N&R hubs. These hubs will be established in EU countries as well as the UK and Ukraine. More than 3000 people who were involved in previously funded SwafS-19 projects will be invited to establish the COALESCE communities of practice (CoP), as well as there being an open invitation for new members to enable a continuous expansion of the community.

COALESCE seeks to transform science communication practice and policy to foster a closer connection between science and society. It will do this in a way that is supportive of existing organisations, networks and individuals, employing an approach that involves co-creation and collaboration. This collaborative approach also informs the communication activities of COALESCE.

The project has initial funding for four years (April 2023 – March 2027) but the Competence Centre is being developed in such a way as to be sustainable in the long term.

1.2 About this guide

This guide is a resource for the N&R hubs and other aforementioned networks associated with COALESCE (referred to as 'networks' below). It is intended to outline the aims of the communication activities but most importantly provide practical guidance on COALESCE-related communication activities. Moreover it proposes ideas for co-organised events that could enhance the dissemination of COALESCE results and describes

co-creation events that will be organised during the project lifetime to co-produce communication materials.

In addition to this guide, N&R hubs will also be provided with a N&R hubs Internal Communication Instructions document, and the networks will be provided with a similar document. These brief instructions guides will describe and support the practical steps of COALESCE communication activities, outlining key communication processes such as the approval process for new communication materials and providing links to resources.

Other activities that can result from the collaboration between COALESCE and the N&R hubs (such as co-organised training courses, sharing resources through the Competence Centre etc.) are not exhaustively tackled in this guide, but will be the focus of other discussions with the hubs.

COALESCE seeks to foster a supportive reciprocal relationship with N&R hubs and networks, in which the hubs and networks raise awareness of Competence Centre and Academy resources and activities through their communication activities and the COALESCE communication team communicates the activities of Hubs and networks.

This guide may be updated periodically to ensure it continues to be a valuable resource. Where updates are implemented, specific changes will be highlighted.

Most of the guide is relevant to both N&R hubs and networks that will form part of the COALESCE ESP. Where information or resources are specific to N&R hubs or networks, this is highlighted in the relevant section.

1.3 National & Regional Hubs

A network of key institutions devoted to science communication (representing the EU27 + the UK and Ukraine) will act as the COALESCE N&R hubs. Thus, a '*glocal*' approach will be used to gather and co-create new knowledge and make it meaningful to national, regional and local quadruple helix (4H) research and innovation (R&I) actors (including researchers, citizens, policymakers and industry), science communication professionals, science and generalist journalists and other actors who communicate science in each country. A key aspect of their work will be to adapt this knowledge to their specific contexts, while promoting mutual learning, training and exchange. Along with the project partners, they will act as physical hubs and multipliers of the Competence Centre in their respective countries. The role of the N&R hubs will be key to mainstreaming excellent science communication across the ERA and increasing the impact of COALESCE. They are directly linked to the CC sustainability strategy.

Initially, the N&R hubs include the 13 COALESCE partners representing eight countries (Spain, The Netherlands, Italy, Estonia, Ireland, Finland, Belgium and the UK), plus five other organisations, enrolled in the beginning of 2024: Koç University (Turkey), SciComPT (Portugal), Center for Research and Analysis (Bulgaria), TRACES (France) and The House of Experiments (Slovenia). Other N&R hubs will be enrolled as the COALESCE project

progresses, up to at least 20 hubs.

The various roles of N&R hubs are outlined elsewhere and so will not be described in detail here. However, in broad terms, they will act as physical hubs of the Competence Centre, organising activities, co-creating resources as well as encouraging and channelling the participation of professionals and stakeholders at the national and regional levels. In addition, they will promote the resources and activities of the Competence Centre and the Academy. The exact nature of the work undertaken by each N&R hub will be defined in discussion with the COALESCE team, throughout the project.

1.4 International, European, National and Regional networks

COALESCE is establishing connections with existing networks that work at an international, European, national and regional level, which will be included in our ESP. Within those, connections with ongoing H2020 and Horizon Europe-funded projects with common or complementary goals (for example European Citizen Science, PATTERN, REINFORCING, Skills4EOSC, etc) for joint communications will be planned to enable wider outreach. Among other things, these networks will connect with existing communities whose members may participate in COALESCE communities of practice and activities as well as contributing to the co-creation of Competence Centre resources.

It is envisaged that networks will promote Competence Centre and Academy resource releases and activities through their internal and external communication channels. At the same time, relevant activities and resources created by the networks will be promoted through COALESCE communication channels.

2 Communication and dissemination goals

This section outlines the communication and dissemination goals of COALESCE as well as describing how communication activities related to the project may support the N&R hubs and networks to achieve their goals.

2.1 COALESCE communication aims

The COALESCE project aims to involve a variety of communities across Europe (and beyond) in bringing about evidenced-based improvements in science communication quality and impact. Therefore a capillary distribution of communication and dissemination activities are crucial to the success of the project and the future of the Competence Centre. Ultimately, this will ensure new approaches to science communication are widely adopted and the rapid mobilisation of science communication in times of crisis. It will also mean that the competences and skills necessary to professionalise the field are disseminated.

The COALESCE Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Strategy describes three aims of its communication activities:

1. Raise awareness, profile and visibility of the activities of the COALESCE project among science communication practitioners (formal and informal), researchers, educators, citizens, industry, journalists and funders across Europe, as well as among national and EU-level policymakers.
2. Share resources, tools and activities of the Competence Centre and the Academy with science communication practitioners (traditional and non-traditional), researchers, educators and funders across Europe, as well as with national and EU-level policymakers, and contribute to the conversation around science communication.
3. Provide responsive communications to support critical situations, providing timely guidance and increasing the reach of relevant COALESCE resources in times of need.

The N&R hubs and networks will play an integral role in the sharing of materials and experiences among European actors and therefore increasing the impact of the project results.

2.2 COALESCE communication and N&R Hub and network goals

Full recognition of the importance of science communication as well as its complexities and professional demands are unfortunately not yet shared by all potential stakeholders and not equally present in all countries. The importance of museums and science centres, science communication organisations as well as freelance professionals and researchers, including those active in public engagement, are too often underestimated and therefore not supported and funded sufficiently. The Competence Centre is a great opportunity to increase the profile of the field, to produce and disseminate recommendations for policy makers, public officers and academic decision makers, and help to support and further develop all science communication actors. The Academy will provide opportunities to fill the gaps in capacity, future-proof communication skills and know-how (also unevenly distributed in the various communities and territories) and encourage the sharing of one's own excellence and experiences, connecting science communication research to practise.

N&R hubs can use their involvement with this larger community in different ways:

1. Enhance their reputation as actors at an European level, which are contributing to build an international network and a structure that will endure in time.
2. Reach new audiences, providing them with information, suggestions and materials that can be outside the current range of the Hub's activities but whom the Hub can be interested in involving to develop new programmes.
3. Provide high quality professional development, hosting COALESCE training courses and/or collaborating in the creation of COALESCE training activities and resources.

At the same time N&R hubs and networks, with their reputation and connections, can help the Competence Centre to reach a critical mass necessary to have an impact on European and connected national policies and practices.

3 COALESCE key audiences

COALESCE communication activities will target a variety of science communication stakeholders in different countries and contexts and will need to be adapted for each audience. N&R hubs and networks will play an essential role in tailoring the messages to these audiences, so they are relevant and understandable to them. Given the nature of N&R hubs' work and connections, different audiences will be accessible to different degrees. In the first instance, we suggest directing the communication activities towards stakeholders that are already connected with the hub at the organisational level. Then, to be strategically aligned with the Hub goals within COALESCE activities, use the opportunity to address other targets with a view to audience development.

Our communication briefings for key launches of Competence Centre and Academy resources and activities (Section 5.2) will provide guidance on the most relevant audiences. However, as an overall guide, three broad audience categories have been identified for COALESCE communication activities:

1. **Primary:** *actively communicating*

These groups serve as the primary target audience for COALESCE CDE activities, because they are (or may wish to be) actively involved in science communication.

a. **Science communicators**

Anyone involved in communicating science on either a part-time or full-time basis.

i. **Professional/traditional**

Those who are employed in a science communication capacity – including public engagement professionals, museum staff, institutional science writers, and public relation officers and press officers in academia, NGOs/CSOs and industry – or those involved in research who devote a considerable amount of time to science communication.

ii. **Informal/non-traditional**

Those who are not formally employed as science communicators, but who undertake science communication on a voluntary basis or who are supported via crowdfunding/sponsorships. This includes science YouTubers / Instagrammers / TikTokers who explain science concepts or research breakthroughs to non-specialist audiences. Also included are those who may not necessarily consider themselves as science communicators, such as those campaigning/protesting for health and environmental issues, who may primarily see themselves as activists/advocates, and those involved in citizen science activities.

b. **Journalists**

Anyone who is employed as a journalist (writer or editor) or who freelances for traditional media outlets (print/TV/radio/online).

i. Science journalists, editors and publishers

Those who specialise in covering one or more sciences.

ii. Journalists, editors, publishers not specialising in science

Those who specialise in other areas of journalism, such as politics or business, but who have to address issues in science in these contexts (e.g. health, climate science, AI) or those who cover topics such as extreme weather events, seismology and health crises without having specialist knowledge in these areas.

c. Researchers, academics and higher education students and staff

Those who work professionally as researchers (whether in academia or industry), and those who are studying science-related degrees at university, as well as other staff, such as those involved in research management-related positions.

d. Science communication researchers

Those who are engaged in conducting research in science communication, generally in academic settings.

2. Secondary: influencing science and science communication

These groups do not necessarily participate in science communication directly but can influence how it is practised and rewarded.

a. Policymakers

Governing bodies, public authorities and administrators of research centres – at local, regional, national or international levels – who are responsible for setting the wider agenda for science communication, and who seek to conduct policy co-design with citizens and researchers and to increase transparency and accountability through citizen engagement.

b. Research funders

Bodies such as the European Commission, national funders such as UKRI in the UK, foundations such as Fondazione Umberto Veronesi in Italy or Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) in Portugal, or charities such as Wellcome Trust in the UK, who are responsible for directly funding research grants and who sometimes require science communication outputs from the research they fund.

c. Funders of science communication / journalism

Organisations – such as Science Foundation Ireland, The Volkswagen Foundation (Germany), Research Foundation – Flanders (FWO), Fondazione Compagnia di San Paolo (Italy), Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT, Spain) – that fund science communication or journalism directly.

3. Tertiary: interested in or affected by science and science communication

COALESCE CDE activities will not focus on these groups but COALESCE outputs may nevertheless be of interest to them.

a. Teachers

Those involved in science education, at all levels.

b. Artists, designers and architects

Those who are inspired by science or who collaborate with scientists for the creation of work; especially those who undertake artistic practice and research that includes participatory methodologies/approaches. This is specially connected to the New European Bauhaus.

c. Citizens

This group is broadly defined and can include those actively participating in informal science communication activities, participatory and policy-based approaches, as well as those groups and communities who are underserved by science communication.

4 Co-organised and co-production communication events

Milestones of the COALESCE project provide the opportunity for N&R hubs and networks to organise local/national events, helping to promote the recognition of science communication and improve its quality at the European level. In 4.1, we provide some ideas for COALESCE related events.

Co-creation events for the production of communication materials will also take place throughout the project lifetime and are briefly outlined in 4.2.

4.1 Opportunities for co-organised events to disseminate key tools and findings

The types of events that N&R hubs and networks might decide to organise to communicate key Competence Centre and Academy resources and findings are illustrated with some examples in this section. However, this is not intended to be an exhaustive list. It is anticipated that once the resources are developed, this will prompt ideas within hubs and networks about events and/or activities with different formats they can organise that will also support their work and aims.

During the COALESCE project **three policy briefs** will be produced: 1. On excellent science communication for urgent societal challenges (such as the climate emergency, health and vaccines, oceans, water and soils, and AI and digital transformation); 2. On excellent science communication for society at large through informal activities (in science museums, festivals, open days, etc); 3. Recommendations to support the academic recognition of

science communication in the European Research Area; as well as other policy recommendations to shape and inform EU science–communication policy.

Beside supporting the impact of policy briefs with the communication activities described in Chapter 5, N&R hubs might organise local public events to present the policy recommendations to local stakeholders. Or they may host smaller, more specialised gatherings of experts and stakeholders to have a deeper discussion on how to apply the recommendations to the local context.

In 2024, a **roadmap and action plan for the rapid mobilisation of science communication in times of crisis** will be published. It will suggest science communication practices and processes that may be used when acute science–related controversies arise. This document will also be translated into a **good practice guide for journalists in times of crises**. Both documents will provide opportunities to organise debates on the topic and the latter could form the basis of a training course.

The first launch of the Competence Centre virtual platform will take place in 2024 and will include the **roadmap** for the rapid mobilisation of science communication in times of crisis, the COALESCE main methodological concept, the **Scicomm Innovation Cycle** and **criteria for excellent science communication**. Two other launches are planned throughout the project, with simultaneous dissemination of integrated tools and resources, such as a **matchmaking tool**, a **pedagogical toolkit**, a **misinformation tool**, the **ENJOI Observatory** and the **Academy**.

For the organisation of all events, please use the relevant contact(s) in Appendix 2 to discuss their implementation and support required.

The dates of the release of key COALESCE resources and reports and a short description of them are provided in the **Timetable of COALESCE Communication Activities** which will be periodically updated. See Appendix 1 for more details about the timetable and where to find it.

4.2 Communication materials' co-production events

Co-production events will be organised involving N&R hubs and representatives of networks to enable communication materials such as videos and infographics to be developed. It is envisaged that one of these will take place each year of the COALESCE project (which ends in March 2027). These events will involve the co-creation of communication materials themselves, as well as idea development to enable N&R hubs and networks to create communication materials at another time, at their own physical venues. The idea generation will involve specific Competence Centre or Academy resources or activities. N&R hubs and networks should adapt the resulting communication materials to their own languages (including national, regional and/or minority languages) and contexts. In addition to the annual events, additional ad hoc online meetings will be organised with N&R hubs and networks when required (subject to the availability of Hub and network representatives) to facilitate the creation of communication materials.

Once determined, the dates of these co-creation events will be provided in the **Timetable of COALESCE Communication Activities** (Appendix 1) which will be periodically updated. These events will be in person where this is feasible, or online when it is not.

5 COALESCE communication: the practicalities

This section provides practical ideas on the implementation of COALESCE-related communication activities by N&R hubs and networks. It also provides links to resources that can be used to support and inform these activities.

5.1 Subject matter of communication activities

While resources and events will be carefully developed for the Competence Centre and Academy, spreading the news about them will be vital to ensure widespread engagement. N&R hubs and networks can play a key role in raising awareness of resources and events among relevant stakeholders in their country or region given their profile, connections and expertise. Events related to COALESCE and organised by N&R hubs and networks themselves will also provide communication opportunities. The COALESCE communication team can support communication activities about these events through its central COALESCE communication outputs, such as the social media channels: X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn and Youtube as well as the News page on the project website and the COALESCE newsletter. Section 6 describes how to inform the COALESCE communication team about activities, so we can help to spread the news.

5.2 How and where communication will take place

Many N&R hubs and networks have large social media presences with a large number of followers, as well as newsletters and events (in person and online). These provide extensive opportunities to connect and share updates with relevant stakeholders.

N&R hubs and networks have extensive experience of the interests and challenges of science communication stakeholders in their own country. It is envisaged that Hubs and networks will use their expertise to tailor communication messages about Competence Centre resources and activities to relevant national stakeholders, such as journalists, museum staff, public engagement specialists and scientists. It is also anticipated that Hubs and networks will communicate in their own national languages, recognising also the importance of any minority languages.

5.3 Briefings to support communication activities

The COALESCE communication team will organise online briefings in advance of the launch of key Competence Centre or Academy resources or events. These will provide key

information to support the communication activities of N&R hubs and networks in relation to these events and resources.

Specifically, during the briefings, we will:

- Provide a short introduction to the resource or event we are about to launch and where any resources/materials can be found.
- Describe any communication resources, such as videos and infographics, we will provide you with to support your communication activities.
- Outline who we envisage to be the key audiences we are targeting at the time; this will depend on the resource or event.

5.4 Resources available – N&R hubs

N&R hubs will have access to the COALESCE Communication Media Kit. The kit provides resources that should be used in any COALESCE-related communication activities they undertake as well as guidance and guidelines on their use. This media kit is available and can be found in each N&R Hub's COALESCE internal folder, managed by the COALESCE Coordination Team with restricted accesses. Information on where to find the Media Kit can be found in the N&R hubs Internal Communication Instructions document. The standard media kit includes:

- A brief fact sheet describing the COALESCE project
- COALESCE logo and visual identity (fonts, colours, etc.)
- A specific N&R hubs COALESCE logo developed following the same visual identity as the original COALESCE logo
- A presentation template
- A letter template
- A video introducing COALESCE

If they have the time and resources to do so, N&R hubs are invited to provide a translation of the captions for the introductory video into their national/regional language. This is a resource N&R hubs can share. Please contact our COALESCE Science Communication and Community Manager (see Appendix 2) for further information on how to do this.

In addition to the general media kit, specific communication resources will be provided in advance of the launch of key Competence Centre and Academy resources and activities, such as the library of resources and pedagogical toolkit to address challenges to effective science–society relations. More information about this can be found in the N&R hubs Internal Communication Instructions document.

5.5 Resources available – Networks

A Media Kit, developed specifically for networks, will be made available to them when key Competence Centre or Academy resources or events are being launched. This kit will include resources created to support communication activities by networks. These might

include short videos, animations, infographics and photos. More information about this can be found in the Networks Internal Communication Instructions document.

5.6 Sharing communication materials with COALESCE (N&R hubs)

When N&R hubs have developed communication resources such as videos and infographics that are related to the Competence Centre or Academy, these should be shared with the COALESCE communication team so the team can plan and distribute the resources through its communication channels. The process to follow, including where materials should be uploaded, how to notify the communication team about new materials uploaded and the approval process are described in the N&R hubs Internal Communication Instructions document.

5.7 COALESCE newsletter

The COALESCE newsletter pulls together content with the objective of informing the European science communication community of the latest news, resources and events that may be relevant to them. It is published every two months and has sections highlighting resources, multimedia and upcoming events.

Please share any resources or multimedia you produce on the topic of science communication with the COALESCE communication team for inclusion in the newsletter. You are also invited to submit science communication events you are involved with, even if they are not organised under the banner of COALESCE. Details of how to contact the COALESCE communication team about items you would like included in the newsletter are provided in the N&R hubs Internal Communication Instructions document.

In addition, please encourage the participants of your events to subscribe to the COALESCE newsletter: <http://coalesceproject.eu/subscribe/>.

5.8 Sharing news and materials on Social Media

N&R hubs and networks are encouraged to follow the COALESCE social media accounts and share, like and comment upon anything that may be of interest to their followers. The COALESCE social media accounts are:

- **X (formerly Twitter):** @scicommEU
- **LinkedIn:** COALESCE SciComm
- **YouTube:** Scicomm EU (COALESCE)

When hubs and networks post news about any COALESCE-related activities they engage in through their social media accounts, they are encouraged to include the COALESCE handles. Posts containing COALESCE-related information or other science communication-related news relevant for COALESCE audiences will be re-shared on COALESCE social media. If the original posts are not in English, a brief translation and/or a short explanation will be provided when re-sharing.

If N&R hubs use social media platforms where COALESCE does not have an account, they are encouraged to acknowledge the connection with the project.

Some of the hashtags we will be using within COALESCE are:

- o Wider science communication and public engagement discourse:
 - #scicomm / #sciencecommunication
 - #citizenscience #citscicomm
 - #publicengagement
 - #sciencetwitter
 - #scichat
 - #scicommchat
- o Events and conferences (for example):
 - #PCST25
 - #Ecsite2024
 - #COP28
- o Topics with science–communication issues:
 - #climatechange
 - #AI
 - #vaccines
 - #health
 - #pollution
- o Specific audiences, for example:
 - #edutwitter (educators)
 - #academictwitter and #PHDchat (researchers)
- o Annual global days to raise awareness for specific issues, where science communication is relevant:
 - #earthday
 - #worldoceansday
 - #mentalhealthawarenessweek
 - #internationalwomensday
 - #worldwaterday

When COALESCE is running a large event, a relevant hashtag such as #COALESCE24 or #ScicommEU24 will be used.

6 Tell us about your activities

Within the COALESCE communications team, we would also like to raise awareness of events and other activities (such as major reports published) by N&R hubs and networks. These activities do not necessarily need to be connected with COALESCE, the Competence Centre or Academy. Our project is connected with organisations and individuals working in science communication and policy across Europe. So through our communication activities, we can raise the profile of the work of N&R hubs and networks, and help them form new

connections. We can also help to recruit participants for events Hubs and networks are organising.

We can let everyone know about what N&R hubs and networks are doing via X, LinkedIn, through our newsletter and on the news page of our website (coalesceproject.eu). Hubs can find guidance on how to let us know about activities in the N&R hubs Internal Communication Instructions document. Networks can find guidance on how to let us know about activities in the Networks Internal Communication Instructions document.

7 Use of the COALESCE brand and approval process - for N&R hubs

This section provides practical suggestions on the use of COALESCE visual materials. It also provides a proposal for the approval process to use and adopt the COALESCE brand. This process will be further developed and improved addressing the inputs and feedback from the N&R Hub representatives.

7.1 Visual identity

The visual identity refers to a cohesive and robust frame built around visual communication to deliver contents to specific target audiences. It comprises diverse elements of visual communication: logo, fonts, and colour palette, that come together under one united aesthetic.

The COALESCE visual identity will be utilised throughout the project's lifetime, to make all communication activities recognisable as part of the COALESCE project, the Competence Centre or the Academy. The details of the use and applications of this visual identity are described in the document called "**COALESCE brand book**". Information on how to access the brand book is provided in the N&R hubs Internal Communication Instructions document.

7.1.1 COALESCE logo

The COALESCE logo was developed within the project consortium with a participatory approach. The complete version (see image below) of the logo is composed by a double C (recalling the concept of the Competence Centre) and the tag-line: Co-creating the EU Competence Centre for Science Communication.

The logo is available in different versions: vertical, horizontal, colour, black, white, with or without the tag-line. All these versions are available both in png and vector formats.

The logo should be used in any of these formats. Please do not stretch, rotate or move the elements within the main logo.

The COALESCE logo is shared with all the N&R hubs representatives in the Media Kit (Section 5.4), and might be used for COALESCE-related communications (e.g. presentation of the project on the N&R hubs website or social media).

As highlighted in section 5.4 of this document, a specific N&R hubs COALESCE logo was developed, following the same visual identity developed for the original COALESCE logo. This also forms part of the Media Kit and might be used for specific COALESCE-related events or activities organised by the N&R hubs.

For official COALESCE-related events organised by the N&R hubs, the official EU disclaimer should be included in all the communication materials.

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7.1.1 COALESCE font

COALESCE adheres to the World Wide Web Consortium's Web Content Accessibility Guidelines ([WCAG 2](#)). The selection of the COALESCE font also followed WCAG 2 guidelines,

using accessible fonts and colour combinations suitable to those with certain visual impairments and in formats accessible by screen readers. Free and open-source software (FOSS) are preferred for the development of COALESCE communications outputs and platforms, including the use of FOSS fonts.

As explained in the image below, the selected COALESCE fonts are:

- DM Serif Display for titles
- DM sans bold for subtitles
- DM sans regular for paragraph

Title

DM serif Display

**Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet,
consectetur adipiscing elit. Aenean
commodo ligula eget dolor. Aenean
massa.**

Paragraph

DM sans regular

DM sans bold

Cum sociis natoque penatibus et magnis dis parturient montes, nascetur ridiculus mus. Donec quam felis, ultricies nec, pellentesque eu, pretium quis, sem. Nulla consequat massa quis enim. Donec pede justo, fringilla vel, aliquet nec, vulputate eget, arcu. In enim justo, rhoncus ut, imperdiet a, venenatis vitae, justo. Nullam dictum felis eu pede mollis pretium. Integer tincidunt. Cras dapibus. Vivamus elementum semper nisi. Aenean vulputate eleifend tellus. Aenean leo ligula, porttitor eu, consequat vitae, eleifend ac, enim. Aliquam lorem ante, dapibus in, viverra quis, feugiat a, tellus. Phasellus viverra nulla ut metus varius laoreet. Quisque rutrum.

DM Serif Display is a high-contrast transitional face. With delicate serifs and fine detailing, the design has been shaped for use in super-sized poster settings. It is accompanied by DM Serif Text, for use in smaller point ranges.

These fonts are licensed under the [Open Font Licence](#). Please use these fonts in all COALESCE-related communication activities.

7.1.1 COALESCE colour palette

COALESCE colour palette is made up of seven colours. All the COALESCE materials already use the COALESCE colour palette. We suggest adopting these colours for any extra communication product to be developed within the project.

Main colors

Variations

7.2 Presentation template

A COALESCE- branded presentation template was developed and is available to N&R hubs in the Media Kit. It can be used and adapted for any COALESCE-related presentations to be realised at national and international level by the N&R hubs.

7.3 Letterhead template

A COALESCE- branded letterhead template was developed and is available in the Media Kit. It can be used and adapted for any COALESCE-related formal communications.

7.4 Licence

Communication and dissemination outputs within COALESCE are shared under open-access licences (primarily the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International Licence – or CC BY-SA 4.0), allowing them to be freely distributed, reused and modified.

7.5 Approval process

An approval process is put in place for communication resources N&R hubs create which include COALESCE branding. Once a communication resource has been uploaded to the Hub ‘Communication repository’ (Section 5.6) Hubs should email COALESCE Science Communication and Community Manager who will carry out a brief check on the resource.

N&R hubs will need to have the use of the branded products approved depending on context. Such an approval process will outline how the branded materials can be used and the contexts in which the materials may be employed. COALESCE reserves the right to request a N&R Hub or network remove communication materials from public view if they do not follow the brand guidelines or may be deemed offensive in some way.

A mechanism to gather feedback is also set in place, to improve the approval workflow and resources provided to the Hubs, to share their experiences regarding the use of COALESCE Communication materials and to collect their suggestions to improve them.

Appendix 1 - Timetable of COALESCE communication activities

A timetable of key communication activities for N&R hubs has been provided in the N&R hubs Internal Communication Instructions document. This will be updated throughout the project. The timetable provides brief descriptions of key activities, such as the release of important Competence Centre or Academy resources, that will be the focal points of communication activities.

Members of the communication team will also be in touch with N&R hubs and networks about key communication events.

Appendix 2 - List of contacts

General COALESCE, Competence Centre and Academy communication enquiries – **Achintya Rao** (COALESCE Science Communication and Community Manager): Achintya.Rao@uwe.ac.uk

COALESCE events – **Paola Rodari**: paola@medialab.sissa.it

COALESCE branding – **Giulia Bonelli**: Giulia.Bonelli@formicablu.it